

Eradication of Institutional Corruption For Sustainable Economic Growth

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INTRODUCTION

We all are well familiar of the corruption and as it is not a new phenomenon in our country. It is a very common poison in the society since ancient time. It is available from the history time of the Mughal and Sultanate period. According to oxford dictionary ,Corruption originates from a Latin word : corruptus. The word is the past participle of corrumpere, meaning “mar, bribe, destroy”. It is not easy to define corruption. But basic definition of corruption is” the misuse of public power (by elected politician or appointed civil servant) for private gain”.It is just like a blood cancer.Now days, it has taken deep roots and is the basic problem for our country that affects each and every section which subsequently affects the development of India by reducing reform infrastructure and provides low quality services to the individuals But in a narrow sense, corruption is mostly concerned with “bribery” and it takes several forms. Corruption is a global phenomenon and it is omnipresent. Corruption has progressively increased and is now rampant in our society.Gradually its, licking our country as a termite and making our country weak and so weak. It has many different shapes as well as many various effects, both on the economy and the society at large.Corruption is exceedling spread in every department whether business, administration, education,hospital,government office and nothing is left. According to Corruption Perception Index (CPI) which ranks 180 countries awards India a score of 40, rendering it the 81st most corrupt country in the world. Developed nations like Ghana, Morocco have also achieved the same score. In today's scenario, in every office one has either to give money to the employee concerned or arrange for some sources to get work done. There is adulteration and duplicate weighing of products in food and civil supplies department by unscrupulous workers who cheat the consumers by playing with the health and lives of the people. In the assessment of property tax the officers charge money even if the house is built properly according to the Government rules and regulations.

Different faces of corruption

Apart from corruption some other problems are serious present issues or faces of corruption which influences many individuals within a society,,which are undermentioned:

- 1) **Bribery:** As the offering, giving, receiving, or soliciting of any item of value to influence the actions of an official or other person in charge of a public or legal duty.
- 2) **Conflict of interest :**A situation exists when two or more contradictory interests relate to an activity by an individual or an institution.
- 3) **Fraud:**A wrongfully representation is made willfully with the intention to deceive the other party.
- 4) **Political corruption:** is the use of powers by government officials or their network contacts for illegitimate private gain.
- 5) **Embezzlement:**It is a theft or misappropriation of funds placed in one's trust or belonging to one's employer.
- 6) **Abuse of discretion:** It means misuse of the power of a judge, public official or a private party (under authority given by contract, trust or will) to make decisions on various matters based on his/her opinion within general legal guidelines.
- 7) **Extortion:** To obtain something by force ,threats or with difficulty.
- 8) **Favoritism:** It is the practice of giving unfair special treatment favoring members of one's own group.
- 9) **Abuse of power for private gain:** Corruption is the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. It can be classified as grand, petty and political, depending on the amounts of money lost and the sector where it occurs.

Causes of Corruption

- 1) **Low pay scale and wages:** In most of the government sector employee getting low salary. Hence some employees revert to corruption for more financial benefits. For example: Recently, the Government increased the salary of the M.P.'s from Rs.16, 000 to Rs.50, 000, that is 300% increase to the existing salary. But there is not attention of government employee.
- 2) **Low job Opportunities:** It is another reason for promote corruption because no job available in market. For example; if a person wants a government job he has to pay lakhs of rupees to the higher officials irrespective of satisfying all the eligibility criteria.
- 3) **Lack of Strict and Fast punishment:** Anyone is found guilty or even caught red-handed by the anti-corruption officials or media, the convicts get less punishment. First, they will be suspended for a few months or weeks and then re-posted to another location with same Job grade and pay.
- 4) **Lack of transparency in affairs and deals:** In many of department fairness and openness is not present. For example: Many seat selection processes like in education, contracts for the job, employee income reports (wealth possession), etc lack of transparency.
- 5) **Options of many political parties:** In India anyone can establish a political party .so there is lot of chance to propel the corruption because every party desire to expand the party all over the world.
- 6) **Lack of Accountability:** In government job, there is a huge trend of corruption because they could not fulfill their duty at per excellence for example If they receive 100 files to be cleared in a week they may not even clear 50 of them in that week. They tend to postpone the clearance of the files.
- 7) **Encouragement of unhealthy competition:** Competition in business is a good symbol and boon for the quality of service to be delivered. But in poor nations, there is an encouragement of unhealthy competition.

8) **Lack of Unity in public:** Public openly criticize corruption but interestingly there is no unity among the public to stop corruption.

Effects of corruption in different sector

1) Effect of corruption by institution

CORRUPTION BY INSTITUTION*

** Percentage of people who think most or all people in the following institutions are corrupt.*

2) Effect of corruption on people

3) Effect of Corruption on business

4) Effects of corruption on education sector

CORRUPTION IN EDUCATION SYSTEM:
‘GALI GALI CHOR HAI..’

- Report of UNESCO-25%-teacher absenteeism-second in the world
- Drain on resources-22.5% waste of education fund
- Politics for teacher appointment ,transfer
- Absent of well established criteria
- Cheating in examination, examination paper leak scam
- Money on the name of entrance test by diff. institutes
- Quota system-lacks transparency
- Need to curb the bribery rackets & corruption rings

5) Effect of corruption on hospital sector

Big scam from 2010 to 2018

YEARS	SCAM	RUPEES
2018	Punjab National Bank Scam	<u>Rs.11,600 crores</u>
2017	<u>Winsome Diamonds and Jewellery scam</u>	<u>Rs.1,530 crores</u>
2016	<u>Man pasand beverages scams</u>	<u>Rs.40 crores</u>
2015	<u>Delhi CNG scam</u>	<u>Rs.100 crores</u>
2014	Hindustan Aeronautics Limited and Rolls-Royce defence scam	<u>Rs.10,000 crores</u>
2013	Vodafone tax controversy-	<u>Rs.11,000 crore</u>
2012	<u>Coal scam</u>	<u>Rs.1.86 lakh crore</u>
2011	Tatra scam	<u>Rs.7.5 billion</u>
2010	Commonwealth Games, Telecom scam	<u>More than Rs.90,000 crores</u>

According to this report last few years, the Indian economy suffered a loss of billion including some of the big scams like Tatra, 2G, the Commonwealth Games, coal, Vodafone, Hindustan Aeronautics, Delhi CNG, Manpasand, Winsome and PNB many more. This is a main reason where Big issues like poverty, education for all, construction, cleaning, unemployment etc continue to remain as issue and fails to climb the wall of corruption.

How to stop / eradicate corruption

- 1) **Give better salary to govt. employee:** Today, private company employee getting high salary rather than govt. employee ie: clerk, office staff etc. So low salary is main problem for divert the mind of govt. employee towards bribe.
- 2) **Strick legal against corrupt person:** This is a better option for curbing the corruption if anti corruption found anyone involved in corruption first he or she suspended that employee from employment and taken for judicial trials, and never show leniency. In other words strong and stringent laws need to be enacted which gives no room for the guilty to escape.
- 3) **Increase the number of vacant people:** Day by day population of our country increase very rapidly and availability of seats in department of every sector very limited. So rest of people are vacant and move towards negative activities which promote crime and corruption.
- 4) **Arrange camera in govt. offices:** For stopping the corruption, first govt. arrange in government offices have cameras to have a watch on employee performance. Now a day, governments do a praiseworthy work for set up cameras in every department of government office.
- 5) **Change time work schedule:** In private offices timing is 8 to 9, but in govt. offices 10 to 5pm, with a lunch break of one hour in between. This indicates how much commitment lies in work and how fast the work goes on.
- 6) **Make media responsible:** today media play a crucial role to expose or fight against corruption, but some time this media deliberately try to hide scandals or corrupt issues. so, if nation want to eradicate and prevent the social issue first it fulfill their obligation honestly.
- 7) **Keep transactions online and provide a bill for every purchase:** Many of them do not pay taxes and escape This involves corruption. Making payments online through bank accounts and provision of bills for every transaction involving money. This is a better corruption watch.
- 8) **Establish Central Vigilance Commission :** There are bodies like CBI (Central Bureau of Investigation) and CVC (Central Vigilance Commission) to look into cases of high officials

getting involved into corruption. There should be no control of the government on these bodies and they should act independently to bring in effective results.

9) **Website for lodging complaints:** Make one website where every citizen of India without any fear or hide their identity do complaint against corrupt activity which is going in society. Now a days government starts in certain states and cities of India who has been permitted for online submission of an FIR / complaint. This is a great start against crime and corruption.

10) **Publicly fund elections.** Where private interests can donate to elections, the state becomes 'legally corrupt.' This undermines checks and balances, because when public officials can be bribed with campaign donations they are more likely to act in the interest of those donors rather than the public interest, or the will of the electorate.

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